

Valorization of Agro-industrial byproducts for high yield Laccase production

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Manuscript details:

Received: 09.04.2026
Accepted: 09.05.2026
Published:30.05.2026

Cite this article as:

Komal Solanke and Aparna Taware (2026)
Valorization of Agro-industrial byproducts
for high yield Laccase production, *Int. J. of
Life Sciences*, 14 (1A): 165-168.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20653907>

Available online on <http://www.ijlsci.in>
ISSN: 2320-964X (Online)
ISSN: 2320-7817 (Print)

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ABSTRACT

Fungal Laccases have higher potential in different industry due to the wide reaction capabilities and broad substrate specificity. Costs and availability of substrates are important factors to consider and therefore the choice of solid substrate plays an important role in determining efficiency in solid fermentation system processes. The objective of this work was to find out substrate for low-cost high profit production of laccase as demand of laccase is high. In this study utilization of Agro industrial biomass waste had applied and various wastes like Tur bagasse, Corn stubs, Soybean bagasse, Groundnut bagasse, Sugarcane bagasse and brewer's spent grain were used. In present experiment native rotting fungi *Peniophora sp* collected and screened for laccase production, Result shows that the activity unit of the different types of substrates is significantly different. The laccase activity unit was higher when Brewers spent grain was used as substrates (0.4044µg/ml) which is 45 times greater than the lowest production by sugarcane bagasse as substrates (0.0090 µg/ml). Experimental results confirmed that the best substrate for laccase production is brewers spent grain with nutrient addition. Further statistical optimization needs to be carried to increase the production of laccase enzyme which will help to bio-eliminate the various industrial phenolic waste compounds.

Keywords: Laccase, Brewers spent grain, *Peniophora sp*, Solid state fermentation.

INTRODUCTION

Laccases are versatile oxidase able to oxidize a diverse range of phenolic and non-phenolic aromatic compounds, their chemical flexibility makes them highly attractive for applications in industries for textile effluent decolorization, pulp and paper bio bleaching and xenobiotic degradation (Wu et al., 2022; Solanke, 2025). However, the industrial use of laccase is still hindered by high manufacturing costs, of which the carbon source can contribute over 70% of the total production cost. To address this, this research focused mainly on the development of low cost fermentation process that utilize abundant agro-industrial residues as substrates has become a major focus in recent years. Solid-state fermentation (SSF) is suitable for processing agro-residues, as it mimics the natural habitat of many fungi, requires limited free water and often yields higher productivities compared with submerged fermentation

al., 2007). Many reports have shown higher laccase production when SSF is performed on agricultural wastes such as wheat bran, sawdust and other lignocellulosic materials, especially when process parameters and nutrient supplementation are optimized (Akermann et al., 2022; Sidhu et al., 2022; Perwez & Al Asheh, 2025). In this context, utilizing BSG as a substrate for laccase production could simultaneously address waste management challenges in industries and also reduce the manufacturing cost of enzyme (Dancker et al., 2025; Nyhan et al., 2023; Zeko-Pivač et al., 2022; Lech & Labus, 2022). The present study evaluates laccase production under SSF using agro-industrial residue like corn stubs, tur bagasse, Soybean bagasse, sugarcane bagasse, groundnut bagasse and brewer's spent grain—as solid substrates. Enzyme yields obtained with these different substrates are compared, with special focus on the performance of BSG relative to other residues and on the economic and environmental implications of BSG as a low-cost substrate for industrial enzyme production.

METHODS AND MATERIAL

1. Collection and isolation of fungal strain

Fruiting bodies of *peniophora* sp. collected from Chhatrapati Sambhajinagar and isolated from fruiting bodies by tissue culture technique and maintained pure mycelial culture on MEA medium.

2. Production of laccase enzyme

Fungal culture of *peniophora* sp. which containing laccase activity were used for work. Standard inoculum (2 mm) of the fungus was cultivated into 250 ml flasks containing different carbon sources were brewer's spent grain, Corn stubs, sugar bagasse, Tur bagasse, Soybean bagasse and Groundnut bagasse. The medium was supplemented with nutrient solution (g/L) pH 5 components were NH_4NO_3 —3; $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$ —3; KH_2PO_4 —5; $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ —0.5; NaCl —0.5; CaCO_3 — 0.5; $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ —0.35; $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ —0.6 (Perdani et al., 2020).

3. Enzyme extraction and Laccase activity measurement

The whole content of flasks were mixed with 50 mL of sodium acetate buffer (50 mm, pH 5.0) and stirred with a rotary shaker at a speed of 120 rpm for 60 min. Then filtered using muslin cloth and centrifuged at a speed of 9000 rpm for 10 min at 4 °C. The crude Laccase obtained in a supernatant, which further tested for the activity. Laccase assay was carried out using a spectrophotometer using Guaiacol as substrate. The reaction mixture comprised 1 mL crude enzyme supernatant, 3 mL sodium acetate buffer and 1 mL Guaiacol it was incubated for 10 min at 30 °C. After 30 s absorbance was measured at 470 nm ($\epsilon_{470} = 12,100 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) (Perdani et al., 2020; Sidhu et al., 2022).

$$i. \quad E.A = A \times V / t \times e \times v$$

{E.A = Enzyme activity A = Absorbance V = Total mixture volume (ml) v = enzyme volume (ml) t = incubation time e = extinction coefficient for Guaiacol (0.6740 $\mu\text{M}/\text{cm}$)}.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In SSF, the low free-water environment and solid surface area favor fungal colonization and enzyme secretion, while avoiding excessive dilution of the product. The present experiment, in which BSG evidently outperforms other substrates under same conditions, further supports the idea that process of fermentation (SSF) and substrate selection (BSG) must be considered together to maximize laccase productivity (Perdani et al., 2020; Revankar et al., 2007; Sharma et al., 2017). Solid-state fermentation of various agro-industrial residues demonstrated a pronounced dependence of laccase production on the nature of the solid substrate. Using Tur bagasse, Corn stubs, Soybean bagasse, Groundnut bagasse and Sugarcane bagasse, low laccase titers occurred, ranging from $0.0090 \pm 0.00086 \mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ (sugarcane bagasse) to $0.0180 \pm 0.0008 \mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ (Tur bagasse). In contrast, brewer's spent grain yielded markedly

higher levels at 0.4044 ± 0.00098 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, which is approximately twenty-fold greater than the values obtained with the other residues. This demonstrates that BSG is a superior substrate for laccase production.

The top tier performance of BSG is accordant with earlier reports in which BSG gave the strong laccase activity among several tested solid substrates, The combination of structural polysaccharides, proteins, and phenolic compounds in BSG likely provides both carbon and nitrogen sources, as well as natural inducers that induces laccase synthesis more effectively than the comparatively less complex agro-residues, These components can sustain robust fungal growth while simultaneously acting as redox-active inducers for ligninolytic enzymes such as laccase. Moreover, the high moisture of fresh BSG (70–85%) reduces the need for water in SSF, aligning with the low-water requirements, validating its role as a versatile, enzyme-supporting feedstock (Liu et al., 2026; Nascimento et al., 2009; Nyhan et al., 2023; Perwez & Al Asheh, 2025). Confirming its suitability as an inducer-rich, attractive, low-cost lignocellulosic support for fungal growth and enzyme production. Similar substrate-specific improvements have been reported for other lignocellulosic wastes like wheat bran in SSF systems using ligninolytic fungi, where the nutrient profile and physicochemical properties of the substrate strongly control enzyme yields (Revankar et al., 2007; Sidhu et al., 2022; Solanke, 2025). Recent studies reveals successful valorization of BSG for the production of cellulases, xylanases and other enzymes, as well as lactic acid and highlighting its potential within a circular bioeconomy framework. From a compositional standpoint, BSG offers several advantages that can explain the observed high enzyme titres. Together with the present SSF laccase data, these examples reinforce the view that BSG is not merely a brewing by-product but a valuable, multifunctional raw material for enzyme biomanufacturing. In addition to higher titres, SSF is more cost effective because it requires simpler reactors, reduced agitation energies, aeration, and lower wastewater generation, all of which can contribute to reduced operating costs relative to SmF. When this is combined with a low-cost carbon source BSG, the cumulative impact on process economics is substantial, especially given that the carbon source alone can account for the majority of enzyme production costs (Akermann et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2026; Nascimento et al., 2009). Thus, the combination

of SSF and BSG not only offers technical advantages in terms of laccase yield but also aligns with the need for economically viable and resource-efficient bioprocesses. From an economic and environmental perspective, utilizing BSG for laccase production directly offers dual purpose solution to industry: waste management in the brewing sector and reducing the financial burden associated with enzyme production.

CONCLUSION

The present study, showing that BSG yields approximately twenty-fold higher laccase activity than other locally available agro-residues under SSF, provides experimental support and validating it as an optimal, low-cost substrate. Combining SSF and BSG maximizes productivity, economics, and sustainability, transforming brewing waste into a multifunctional bioresource. Future work should optimize process parameters and scale-up for industrial laccase biomanufacturing.

Acknowledgement:

The authors are very grateful to the university grants commission (UGC), New Delhi, India for providing funding's through Research fellowship (JRF) and Research centre Deogiri Collage Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar for providing facilities to carrying out this work.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable.

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